

Early prediction of student performance in a programming class using prior code submissions and metadata

Nazia Alam
North Carolina State
University
nalam2@ncsu.edu

Halim Acosta
North Carolina State
University
hacosta@ncsu.edu

Kevin Gao
North Carolina State
University
kgao@ncsu.edu

Behrooz Mostafavi
North Carolina State
University
bzmostaf@ncsu.edu

ABSTRACT

Early prediction of student performance is a challenging research problem. In this study, we aim to address this problem in a programming class. We use a dataset containing code submissions and associated metadata from programming problem assignments in a CS programming course. We use this data to predict students' final exam scores in the course. We investigate the use of deep learning based advanced machine learning approaches such as the convolutional neural network (CNN) based code embeddings, and long short-term memory networks (LSTM) to find out the effectiveness of these methods for predicting student performance. In addition, we looked into the use of Halstead features from code submissions in order to augment our models with more code-specific information. We evaluate and compare these deep learning methodologies against various traditional machine learning approaches. Empirical findings show that the LSTM model using metadata outperformed all the other machine learning methods for early prediction of student final exam scores. Our findings provide insight into the use of advanced machine learning models for prediction of student performance and early identification of at risk students, and can aid in determining whether additional support and pedagogical intervention are needed for any student.

1. INTRODUCTION

Predicting student performance is an active research topic in the educational realm, as it provides great insight into understanding why certain students are able to achieve the learning outcomes in their courses, while others struggle to

do the same. If students who are at risk of failure can be identified beforehand, then early intervention can help said students avoid poor academic results, in the form of timely provision of additional guidance and personalized assistance.

While there has been a fair amount of research in predicting student performance, fewer studies have been performed in the context of Computer Science programming assignments. Computer Science has some unique domain-specific challenges associated with it, such as effectively leveraging CS-specific aspects of the data (source code). In this study, we aim to address these challenges in order to predict student performance in an introductory programming class. We use data from a CS programming course at a public university in the U.S which contains the code submissions and other metadata from students for programming problem assignments. We use this data to predict students' final exam grade in the course.

In recent years, deep learning and other advanced machine learning models have achieved some groundbreaking results in many domains. For this study we investigated several deep learning approaches. The data we use contains time series data of each student's code submissions and metadata over a sequence of 30 coding problems. LSTM models can effectively learn long-term sequential dependencies in time series data, thus making them an ideal choice for our problem; hence, we chose to explore the use of LSTMs for predicting student performance in this study.

Student source code snapshots can provide rich information concerning a student's progression through a problem, their algorithmic thinking, and can convey information related to why a student may produce erroneous solutions. They also function as formal descriptions of executable tasks and can convey programming intent. ASTs (Abstract Syntax Trees) extracted from source code have the added benefit of capturing code paths providing contextual information in addition to structural information. A CNN applied to source code can exploit the rich structural information present in student source code; furthermore, applying convolutional operations across an AST's tree-based structure can provide contextual information based on the node relationships, which benefits downstream classifiers. This led to our other approach in creating a code embedding from the code submissions using

the CNN model and a FFNN for predictions.

Halstead features are a unique way to describe the code quality. They can be used to predict defects and errors in the code. In the context of the classroom setting, the choice to use the Halstead metrics seemed to be apt, as these metrics directly measure difficulty, error quantity, and effort, all of which relate to the nature of academic coursework. We hypothesize that these features would lend themselves well to our problem. For our experiment, we generate Halstead features from the code submissions to provide the models with more code-specific information, and use them with deep learning models as well as some baseline models to investigate any differences.

Overall our main contributions in this study are as follows: we employ deep learning based advanced machine learning approaches and evaluate their effectiveness for the task of predicting student performance in a programming class. We compare the performance of the deep learning models with the traditional machine learning models. We also investigate the use of Halstead features for predicting student performance. Finally we conclude by stating possible future works.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been a number of studies to predict student performance using machine learning approaches. Conijn et al [4] conducted a study on predicting student performance in a blended MOOC where student performance is defined by the final exam grade. The data contained features such as general activity frequencies, specific course item frequencies, and order of MOOC activities and performance data. The study used multiple linear regression method to predict final exam grade using MOOC activity variables as predictors. Another study [5] tried to predict applicants' future academic performance in a Master of Data Science program using information from the admission application. It uses features such as standardized test scores, undergraduate grade point average, declared major, and school ranking. It used prediction models such as SVM, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, KNN, Naive Bayes, Neural Network and also an ensemble method. It found that the Random Forest and the ensemble learner achieved the two best overall predictive accuracy. Delianidi et al [3] proposed to use dynamic neural models to predict student knowledge state and student performance in the next exam. They experimented with two different dynamic neural networks- a recurrent bidirectional GRU model and a Time Delay neural network (TDNN) model. They used a dynamic time window length L (50) that contains the recent history of inputs and outputs. Hasib et al [17] attempted to predict student performance using real-world data from two Portuguese secondary schools. They used classification models such as Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors(KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), XGBoost, and Naive Bayes. Results showed that SVM achieved the highest accuracy among these models. Koutina et al [21] experimented with six classification algorithms namely decision tree, k-nearest neighbors Naive-Bayes (NB) classifier, RIPPER (Repeated Pruning to Produce Error Reduction), Random Forest and SVM to predict academic performance of post-graduate students. Their study found that Naive Bayes and

KNN achieved the best results. Xu et al [18] tried to predict student performance such as final GPA in a degree program. They proposed a novel algorithm for making predictions which adopts a bi-layered structure consisting of a base predictor layer and an ensemble predictor layer. Simulation studies on an undergraduate student dataset from UCLA showed that the proposed method outperform benchmark methods. Harley et al [19] worked to predict student performance (SAT math scores) in K-12 education. They experiment with three classifiers including linear regression, decision tree, and Naive Bayes techniques. Results showed that the Naive Bayes achieves the highest accuracy when predicting SAT math scores. Rastrollo-Guerrero et al [20] conducted a review on the papers on the topic of student performance prediction using machine learning. They found that the most widely used technique for predicting students' behavior was supervised learning and specifically the SVM algorithm was the most used by the authors.

There has been a few studies to predict student performance in programming domain. Hellas et al [28] conducted a systemic literature review on predicting academic performance which also included CS domain papers. They found that statistical methods such as linear modeling were the most common, and graph models and decision trees were also common. Ihtola et al [29] performed a literature review focused on teaching and learning programming where they review a number of studies on identifying at risk students and measuring student performance. Buenaño-Fernández et al [22] conducted a study where they tried to predict final grade of computer engineering students based on historical performance. The authors used a Decision Tree model as the classification model. Another study from ElGamal [23] also used decision tree algorithm to predict student performance in a programming course. Authors made use of features such as High school mathematics grade, mathematical background, programming aptitude, previous computer programming experience, gender, etc. Watson et al [24] proposed a unique algorithm which generates a score called Watson score where a student is relatively penalized based upon the amount of time they take to resolve a specific type of error compared to other students. They used this score with linear regression to predict coursework marks in a programming course. However, the score focuses on one compilation behavior, and ignores other programming behaviors. Carter et al [25] proposed a model called Normalized Programming State Model (NPSM) for characterization of students' programming processes in order to predict student performance in a programming course. The model maps a student's programming activity to one of 11 different states. For each student, the amount of time spent in each state is recorded and then normalized. These are used by the NPSM with linear regression to predict students' grades on individual assignments, students' overall assignment average, and students' final grades. However, the model only focuses on time spent by students in different programming activities. Araya et al [26] proposed several metrics including skill related metrics, work habit related metrics, and a similarity score to predict student performance. The scores were used to predict student performance in a data structure course with linear regression, random forest, and SVM algorithms. It was found that the random forest model did comparatively better.

Source code embeddings techniques are concerned with transforming human written code into a format that computers can understand. It allows us to design models that can understand program behavior, look for source code bugs, and identify specific programming styles or paradigms. Further, program embeddings can be used to solve downstream software engineering tasks for which program language processing is important [9, 10]. There have been a few proposals for effective code embeddings such as Code2Vec [11], recurrent neural networks [12, 15]. It has been shown that CNNs excel at exploiting the rich and explicit structural information present in source code [13]. Mou et al [14] developed a tree-based convolutional architecture (TBCNN) that takes as input a programs abstract syntax tree and produces a vector representation for the tree that is then utilized in a downstream classifier for classifying code snippets and classifying programs by functionality. They propose a novel tree based convolutional filter that utilizes separate weights for node locations and employs a “continuous” binary tree by coding weights to deal with the variable size of the AST children’s nodes. They find that their method is able to outperform other baseline methods that utilize code embeddings.

3. DATASET

The Dataset we are using for our study is the data from the 2nd CSEDM Data Challenge[1], which is available at the PSLC Datashop website [2]. The data was collected from CodeWorkout, a free online system for beginner or novice programmers. The CodeWorkout dataset is collected from a CS1 course in the Spring and Fall 2019 semesters at a public university in the U.S. The fall dataset, like the spring dataset, had already been split into a training and a testing set and were provided on the PSLC website. However, we combined both the spring and the fall training data together in order to increase the effectiveness of our models.

The dataset contains code submissions from students for 50 coding problems, each requiring 10-26 lines of code in Java. There were 329 and 490 students in the Spring and Fall semesters, respectively, who completed the course. Each semester dataset contains 65K+ code submissions. The complexity of the coding problems increased as the course progressed. The initial problems were based on simple concepts, while later problems were based on more complex concepts. The data also contains additional information, including identifiers (e.g. ProblemID, AssignmentID), a time instance, tool instance, EventType (whether it was a code compilation or runtime event), and the result of compiling the code (success or fail).

The dataset also contains metadata for each student such as the number of attempts, whether the students struggled (attempted the problem but never got the problem correct, or got the problem correct but required more attempts to do so than 75% of other students who attempted the problem), and whether the students were correct eventually or not for each of the attempted programming problem. The training data comes from first 30 programming problems in the course, which is a little over halfway through the course. We discuss in section 4 how we utilize all the relevant metadata in our methodologies, and outline their utility in our data pre-processing.

4. METHODOLOGIES

In this section, we discuss the features and machine learning models used in the study.

4.1 Halstead Metrics

There are various ways to perform student grade prediction using features such as activity frequency or course item frequency; these come directly from the graded material of the students. For our study, we chose to utilize the Halstead Complexity Metrics. Invented by Maurice Halstead in 1977, the idea behind the metrics is to treat a computer program as a collection of tokens, classifying each token as either an operator or operand, then getting the counts of each token class. These counts, along with other metrics, can be used to measure and describe software quality, code correctness, and sustainability of code.

Regression models used for predicting student performance have substantial presence in existing literature; however, few works discuss the direct use of Halstead metrics as the predictors of code quality, and even fewer for student academic performance. Santos et al [6] used Halstead metrics to describe pieces of source code; this was to show that those features could be used to predict possible defects in future versions of the code (software version control). Huang and Fang [16] detailed the relationship between the Halstead metrics and student academic performance in an engineering course using various machine learning techniques. Despite the low amount of references, the relevant literature led us to believe that the Halstead Metrics could potentially be adequate predictors of student performance in an education setting.

4.1.1 Halstead Standardized Definitions

As per the CMT standards [27], the Halstead Metrics are defined as follows:

- n_1 = number of unique operators
- n_2 = number of unique operands
- N_1 = total number of operators
- N_2 = total number of operands
- N = program length: $N_1 + N_2$
- n = size of vocabulary: $n_1 + n_2$
- V = program volume: $N * \log_2(n)$
- D = program difficulty level: $(n_1/2) * (N_2/n_2)$
- L = program level i.e. inverse of error proneness: $1/D$
- E = effort to implement: $V * D$
- T = time to implement: $E/18$
- B = number of delivered bugs: $E^{(2/3)}/3000$

CMT’s official website defines the standard for operators and operands for many commonly used languages; using the website’s guidelines, we built our own Java based corpus of terms as follows: Unique operators include:

- all reserved words, as defined by Oracle’s Java API references. These include class descriptors like *abstract* and *implements*, function descriptors such as *public* and *private*, and common words like *if/else* and *for*.
- non alpha-numeric symbols, such as +, -, /, (), *, ||, etc. Also includes logic and bitwise operators.
- type qualifiers. An example would be *const*.

Unique operands include:

- type specifiers, such as bool, char, double, int, etc.
- constants: includes characters, numeric and string constants
- any other identifiers that are not reserved words

The full list of operators and operands can be found on the Verifysoft Technology site [27]¹.

4.1.2 Data Pre-processing With Halstead Metrics

We wanted a streamlined method for determining the contribution of each code submission to the student’s final grade. Because we weren’t using pre-defined KCs (Knowledge Components), we could not track whether they learned certain concept or retained it, such as in BKT (Bayesian Knowledge Tracing). Thus, we simplified our process as such: we calculated the Halstead metrics for every code submission. We then aggregated the Halstead metrics for each student to get a single vector of features; first by averaging all the metrics over all submission per problem, then by averaging out the previous aggregation results over all problems per assignment, and lastly, by taking those results and averaging them out over all assignments per student. The final results are the features on which we fit our models.

4.2 Code Embeddings with CNNs

In this work we explored the source code embedding techniques. Recent work has shown some success utilizing tree-based architectures such as Tree-based convolutional neural networks [14]. We worked to implement a preliminary version of the CNN based architecture. The model consists of a trainable embedding layer followed by a one dimensional convolutional layer and a global max pooling operation. In order for us to apply this embedding in a hierarchical fashion we employ a time distributed layer such that the aforementioned layers are applied to each sequence in the tree separately. We also performed hyper-parameter tuning of the various components of the model. Finally, we will need to perform a comparison between various CNN based architectures to investigate the effectiveness of the embeddings for downstream classifiers.

¹Full Description of Halstead Operators/Operands at: https://www.verifysoft.com/en_halstead_metrics.html

4.2.1 Data Pre-processing

In order to utilize source code information in our models we applied a series of pre-processing methods. We first augment the source code so that they represent valid java files because the underlying abstract syntax tree generator must have a fully compiling program in order to generate a valid tree. Any non-compiling source code must be processed for each line to generate their AST node representation however you lose the underlying tree structure. Once the syntax trees have been generated, each node has its string representation tokenized and placed in a vector representing its location in the vocabulary. These vectors will serve as input to our code embedding model.

4.2.2 Convolution-Based Architectures

In order to capture the rich structural information present in student programs, we evaluated four different convolutional neural network architectures. Each architecture was used to generate an embedding of students’ code by utilizing abstract syntax trees. For the ASTs to be usable by deep learning models they first needed to be vectorized. Each node in an AST consists of information related to its structure (Compilation unit, Class declaration, Variable declaration, etc.) as well as information related to any values variables may take on among others. Since all node information is in string format, we must vectorize each node to turn into a numerical representation. Due to this the first layer of the model consists of a text vectorization layer that pre-processes textual input and maps it to an integer sequence. The primary pre-processing that happens in this layer is that all text is stripped of punctuation and tokenized based on white space separation. To generate a vector of sequences that represents the entire AST we stack the vectors for each node of the AST following the breadth-first traversal of the tree. This follows the order of generation for each node and maintains the overall structure of the text-based AST. Finally, because the goal of the project was to predict students’ final grades based on their programming behavior on the first thirty problems, we stack the vectorized AST from each problem submission that has a successful compilation. Because ASTs may differ in depth all sequences are either padded or truncated to a fixed length. Students had a large number of problem submissions resulting in a very large vector representation of a student’s history due to each AST sequence consisting of a sequence of vectors. Due to hardware constraints, we limited the size of this vector to size 5000 which represents 5000 nodes following the breadth-first traversal across all successful compilation submissions resulting in a vector of (5000, 50) for each student where 5000 is the number of nodes and 50 is the maximum length of each nodes vector representation.

4.2.3 Embedding Module

This pre-processed data is passed to a neural network model that consists of 3 sub modules: the embedding module, the convolutional module, and the final inference module. The convolutional module was designed and tested with three different convolutional architectures that will be explained in section 4.2.4. The embedding module consisted of a simple embedding layer that takes positive integer indices and converts them into dense vectors of fixed size. This layer is set to be trainable so that the model can learn the correct

embedding representation for each of the nodes in the abstract syntax tree. This layer is followed by a batch normalization layer normalizes that data at batch level and helps to improve the model’s performance by restricting the mean of the data to close to 0 and a standard deviation of 1. To make sure that we create an embedding for each node in the AST we apply a time distributed layer which will apply the entire embedding over all student trees. This comprises the entirety of the embedding module for our model.

4.2.4 Convolutional Module

The second sub module for our model consists of different variations on the convolutional neural network architecture. Specifically, we design and evaluate a concatenation-based CNN, a deep CNN, and a skip connection architecture. The concatenation-based CNN works by applying separate convolutional layers to the input from the embedding layer and concatenating them together. This allows each individual CNN layer to learn different feature representations that the inference layer can utilize. The deep CNN works by adding a batch normalization layer to the output of the CNN before applying the activation function. These CNN-Batch Normalization-Activation blocks are then chained together in order to increase the model’s receptive field. Finally, the skip connection inspired architecture makes use of the same CNN blocks as used in the deep CNN architecture however it the model is deeper and utilizes skip connections in order to mitigate the degradation problem that can arise from deeper architectures and helps to ensure feature reusability.

4.2.5 Inference Module

The final sub module is the inference layer of the network. Its primary purpose is to utilize the features extracted from the CNN and embedding sub modules and make predictions of student’s final course grades. This module consists of a simple two-layer feed-forward neural network with a final output layer using rectified linear units that caps its output at 100. The entire model is an end-to-end embedding and inference model where the embedding vectors are learned during model training. Each section of the model, with the exception of the embedding sub module, was hyper-parameter tuned using Bayesian optimization with a Gaussian process. Bayesian optimization performs hyper-parameter tuning using Bayesian inference to choose the next best hyper-parameters based on the previous best working hyper-parameters. We individually did optimization for each of the CNN sub module architectures and utilized the best hyper-parameters when evaluating the model on the final test data.

4.2.6 Evaluation

We evaluated the models initially on a held-out validation set consisting of twenty percent of the total training data. We used the results from the validation runs in order to choose the best model for the final test data set consisting of the Fall 2019 data set. The best model then trained on the all of the training data using early stopping to stop model over fitting and was then run on the test data. From the results we can see that the CNN architecture that worked best were the concatenation-based CNN. In fact, the more complex models tended to have a decline in predictive performance which is likely due to the small number of unique students in the training set (approx. 615 students). This

is most exemplified with the skip connection architecture where it has a validation set MSE of 385 compared to MSE of 244 for the validation set MSE found by the concatenation-based architecture. We anticipate that with a large data set and some regularization strategies the model’s performance could be improved more. What we find is that the deeper models tend to over-fit to the training data while stagnating on the validation data which is a problem with deeper models. Further, despite the skip connections present in the skip connection architecture, which ideally should mitigate the degradation problems, the model still tends to over-fit to the training data and has trouble generalizing.

4.2.7 Combined Halstead Features

We hypothesized that the models would reach a natural limit in the predictive performance if only allowed to use the students code samples. To try and improve this upper limit we combined the code-based features extracted from the CNN architecture with generated features based on the already compiled Halstead complexity measures, along with other student metadata from the datasets. We posited that these features would allow the model to try and understand the style inherent in each student’s code as well as incorporate specific student behaviors such as the average number of attempts per problem, the number of correct submissions, etc. We evaluated all of the above architectures in conjunction with these features and noticed a small improvement in predictive performance for concatenation based CNN as well as the deep CNN architecture.

4.3 Long short-term memory (LSTM) networks

The dataset contains a sequence of metadata for each student such as the number of attempts, whether the students struggled, and whether the students were correct eventually or not for each of the attempted problem. These data are available for 30 sequential programming problems. Recurrent neural networks, specially LSTM models are known for their applicability on sequence data, therefore in this study we make use of LSTM network on the metadata. LSTM is a variant of RNN which contains feedback connections. Each LSTM unit contain a number of gates which controls how a sequence of data comes into and leaves the network. There are three gates in a LSTM unit: forget gate(the gate that controls what the cell should forget), input gate(the gate that controls the input), and output gate (the gate that controls the output from the unit). The sequence of metadata for each student are used as input to the LSTM network. The sequence may vary in length as all students may not have attempted all of the thirty problems, in those cases the sequences are padded to a fixed length (30).

4.4 Baseline Models (Traditional Regression Models)

To gauge the overall effectiveness of our approach we established a baseline for comparison: a set of baseline models were chosen based on how often they appeared in previous similar studies. These include Linear Regression, Ridge Regression, Lasso Regression, Bayesian Ridge Regression, K-Neighbors Regression, and Support Vector Regression. We also utilized various existing ensemble methods, including Random Forest Regressor, Bagging Regressor, Stacking Re-

gressor, and Voting Regressor. We trained our baseline models on the data using the Halstead Metrics as features.

5. EXPERIMENT

A list of all the parameters that were used for the best performing models can be found in Table 1.

5.1 Research Question

The question we are addressing is: Given a student’s submission history and metadata for the first 30 programming problems which was a little over halfway through the course, can we effectively predict students’ final exam grades in the course?

5.2 Experimental settings and parameters

Table 1: Experiment parameters

Parameter	Values
CNN code embedding	
Learning rate	0.001
Number of units	56
Optimizer	Adam
Kernel size	2
Filter size	48
regularizer	L2
LSTM	
Learning rate	0.0001
Number of units	20
Optimizer	Adam
Support Vector Regressor	
kernel	rbf
C	1.0
epsilon	.1
gamma	.1
Random Forest	
n estimators	100
max depth	unlimited
Bagging Regressor	
base estimator	SVR
n estimators	10

5.2.1 CNN based code embedding with feed forward neural network

Hyper-parameter tuning was done using Bayesian optimization. For the CNN models we optimized over the size of the convolutional kernel which is concerned with the size of the sliding window over the AST. This ranged between 32 and 512 length windows. We also optimized for the number of filters over a range from one to four filters governing the dimensionality of the output space. The inference sub module was optimized for the type of regularizer used, either L1 or L2 regularization as well as the number of units to use for the hidden layers. Finally, the entire model was tuned to find the best optimizer and learning rate combination that most improved the model performance. We tested Adam, RMSprop, and AdaDelta optimization algorithms with a learning rate that varies between 0.01 to 1^{-5} . The hyper-parameters are shown in Table 1.

5.2.2 LSTM

For this study we used a simple network with 1 LSTM layer on the Fall and Spring training data. We used 20% of the data as validation data for tuning hyper parameters such as number of units, learning rate and optimizer. We applied grid search to select the optimal values. For learning rate we explored the values [0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001, 0.00001, 0.000001]. We explored the number of units in the LSTM layer in the range [5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30]. For optimizer we tested Adam and SGD to find the optimal parameters. The selected hyperparameter values can be found in Table 1.

5.2.3 Baseline Methods

For Linear Regression, we ran 5-fold CV. For Ridge and Lasso Regression, we ran GridSearchCV, checking alpha values in [0.02, 0.024, 0.025, 0.026, 0.03]. For K Neighbors Regression, we checked [3,4,5,6,7,8,9] for the number of neighbors, and we used 'minkowski' for the distance parameters. For SVR, we did GridSearchCV for parameters C, epsilon, and gamma. For C, we checked 'C': [0.1, 1, 2, 5, 10, 100, 500, 1000]; for epsilon, we checked 'epsilon': [0.0001, 0.001, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 1, 5, 10]; for gamma, we checked 'gamma': [0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 1, 3, 5].

Upon determining the best baseline model, we then used that model as the base estimator in the Bagging Regressor model, and as the final estimator in the Stacking Regressor model. For the Voting Regressor, we used the top 2 best individual baselines models as the estimators. For the Random Forest Regressor, we checked [50,75,100,125,150] for the number of estimators, but left auto-scaling on for the branching factor and max depth.

5.3 Performance Metric

Mean Square Error (MSE): MSE is the one of the most widely used metric for regression tasks and is the averaged squared difference between the actual value and the value predicted by the model. The formula is:

$$MSE = \frac{\sum (f - o)^2}{N}$$

where, f = predicted values, and o = actual values, N = number of data points. Since ours is an regression work, we use MSE as the performance metric.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We trained the prediction models and predicted the final exam grade (scored out of 100) using the Fall 2019 test data. The performance of the models are displayed in Table 2.

We started with using only the Halstead features. There is a set of Halstead features per student. We used the Halstead features with various traditional machine learning models to find out its applicability. We found that the best baseline model was the BaggingRegressor ensemble applied to our tuned SVR model; it resulted in an MSE of 276.98. With regular SVR tuned with the aforementioned parameters, it resulted in an MSE of 278.15. Random Forest Regression resulted in an MSE of 295.08, and K-Neighbors Regression resulted in an MSE of 303.63. All other baseline models resulted in a higher MSE value.

Table 2: Performance of the machine learning models

Model	MSE value
BaggingRegressor (SVR as base) on Halstead features	276.98
StackingRegressor (Bagging as final) on Halstead features	277.31
VotingRegressor (SVR and RF) on Halstead features	277.41
SVR on Halstead features	278.15
Random Forest on Halstead features	295.08
KNN Regression on Halstead features	303.64
Lasso Regression on Halstead features	320.65
Bayes Ridge Regression on Halstead features	357.38
Ridge Regression on Halstead features	399.73
Linear Regression on Halstead features	452.5
CNN on student code	247.87
CNN on student code + Halstead features	244.18
LSTM on the metadata	231.85
LSTM on the metadata + Halstead features	262.27

Table 3: Feature importance with combined Training Data for the BaggingRegressor model

n1	0.13807
n2	0.10413
N1	0.09402
N2	0.11925
N	0.05785
n	0.08535
V	0.09237
D	0.05679
L	0.08552
E	0.05082
T	0.05459
B	0.06124

As an afterthought, we ran feature importance tests for the Halstead features for the top performing traditional machine learning models (see Table 3). The feature importance values were calculated using feature importance functions from scikit-learn, which calculates impurity-based feature importance using the GINI index. We ran these tests in order to check how adequate the set of features were in predicting the regression outcomes, as well as seeing if the resulting values could provide us with any insight into the effectiveness of our prediction models, which potentially could have led to us to utilizing dimensionality reduction or improved feature selection, both of which our models would benefit from.

For the Fall training set, the most important features were n1, n2, N1, and N2. The same was found for the combined training set. This does make sense, as the rest of the Halstead complexity metrics are calculated using the first 4 features which are n1, n2, N1, and N2. However, when we ran our best models again to fit on just the first 4 features, we ended up with lower MSE scores across all the models, with an average dip in 30-40 points in the MSE. In analyzing the feature importance scores, we posit that the reason why our models required all features is because while the first 4 features were the most important, they were only slightly more important than the rest, with the biggest difference being only a .07 difference in scores. Thus, we conclude that a lot

of the captured variance observed by the models was lost when we trained the models again by removing the other 8 features.

After analyzing the effectiveness of the Halstead features by its own, we investigated the impact of using them together with other features. First we applied the CNN based model on the student code embedding, and then on the code embedding and Halstead features together. Similarly, We applied the LSTM model on the metadata, and then on the metadata and Halstead features together.

LSTM models are known for being one of the most suitable models for sequence data, which proved to be the case in this study. From the Table 2, the results show the LSTM model trained only on the metadata got the lowest MSE of 231.85. The metadata used by the LSTM was formatted in a sequential nature; each student did each programming task in successive order. The result from this shows that the features contained in the metadata such as number of attempts, whether the students struggled, and whether the students were correct eventually, are all potential strong predictors for predicting student performance. Compared to baseline methods, the LSTM outperformed the top regression models by about 45-64. Figure 1 shows the actual final exam grades of students vs the prediction from LSTM. Applying the LSTM on the metadata combined with Halstead features resulted in an MSE of 262.27, which was higher than what was achieved with only the metadata. Since the data size is small (about 615 students), adding more features could potentially overfit the model, which might explain the increase in MSE.

Following the 2 LSTM methods, the CNN model using student code embeddings and Halstead features got 244.18 MSE, putting it in close comparison with the first two methods. Comparing the results for the CNN based architectures, we find that including the Halstead complexity features improves the models performance by small margin. This is likely due to the difference in model architecture. When utilizing the complexity features, an auxiliary layer FFNN (Feed Forward Neural Network) takes the features as input and combines its vector representation of the features with the CNN representation before passing it through a final

Figure 1: Comparison of actual final exam score vs prediction from LSTM model using metadata

layer. This secondary representation may help the model learn more about the students code; however, the small increase in performance might hint at a possible upper limit to what can be learned from the code submissions alone. An alternative may be to combine these features with other student metadata to allow the model to learn different relationships within the data although this may cause a degradation problem if the number of student samples remains the same.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In terms of limitations, one possible area for improvement would be how we did the initial rounds of aggregation on the datasets when creating the baseline Halstead features. It is possible that the method we used for aggregating all the code submission features together might not have accurately capture the state of the dataset; not all students answered every question or submitted for every assignment, and we also do not know how much of the final grade each assignment counts for, with the assumption that all assignments contributed equally to the final grade.

We employed deep neural networks which often require a large amount of training samples in order to be effective. Our dataset only consisted of 615 students, and our models used a large number of features for some of the experiments. This can lead the model to over fit to the training data and have troubles with generalizability. A further limitation of the CNN model is that all ASTs were required to be padded to the same size which may obscure some of the structural properties. Some more structural information may be lost due to having to stack ASTs in order to get a single vector representation of students submission history. A final limitation of the CNN based embedding is that it was not compared against other embedding techniques such as Code2Vec which would help to give a better understanding of whether the embedding space exhibits comparable inter-cluster separation and intra-cluster similarity

Future work would explore different code embedding archi-

tectures such as ones that combine the structural representation learning from the CNN and the sequential learning properties of LSTM architectures. Further, different ways of combining the generated Halstead features with both the code embeddings and student metadata could be explored that would take better advantage of the information present in each data channel. An analysis of the quality of the embedding space should also be conducted to further evaluate the efficacy of the learned code embeddings. In this study we only applied an LSTM with a single layer however we could explore different architectures such as bidirectional or stacked LSTMs. Since the dataset has a relatively low number of unique student samples we could explore other regularization strategies to stabilize network training. Finally, the baseline machine learning models could be trained with available metadata along with Halstead features.

8. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we applied advanced machine learning methods to predict student performance based on the code submissions and metadata from a set of programming problems. An ablation study of various convolutional architectures was conducted to explore which models would be most effective in predicting student grades directly from student source code submissions. We implemented a LSTM neural network to take advantage of the sequential nature of student submissions. Moreover, we employed Halstead complexity measures on student code to generate additional features to enhance our devised models predictive performance. Our results show that LSTM using metadata outperformed the other machine learning models for the task of predicting students' final exam score. Overall this study demonstrates that code submissions and metadata can be used for early prediction of students' final exam grade, which can aid in optimizing pedagogical decisions to make sure that students' can successfully achieve their learning outcome.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] 2nd EDM data challenge. <https://sites.google.com/ncsu.edu/csedm-dc-2021/>
- [2] CodeWorkout data. <https://pslclatashop.web.cmu.edu/DatasetInfo?datasetId=3458>
- [3] Delianidi, Marina, Konstantinos Diamantaras, George Chrysogonidis, and Vasileios Nikiiforidis. "Student Performance Prediction Using Dynamic Neural Models." EDM conference (2021).
- [4] Conijn, Rianne, Antoine Van den Beemt, and P. Cuijpers. "Predicting student performance in a blended MOOC." *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 34, no. 5 (2018).
- [5] Zhao, Yijun, Qiangwen Xu, Ming Chen, and Gary M. Weiss. "Predicting Student Performance in a Master of Data Science Program Using Admissions Data." *International Educational Data Mining Society* (2020).
- [6] Santos, Geanderson, Eduardo Figueiredo, Adriano Veloso, Markos Viggiano, and Nivio Ziviani. "Predicting software defects with explainable machine learning." In *19th Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality*, pp. 1-10. 2020.
- [7] Prabowo, Yulius Denny, Harco Leslie Hendric Spits Warnas, Ford Lumban Gaol, Edi Abdurachman, and Benfano Soewito. "An initial research on Halstead's technique for pattern similarity relationship study." In *2018 International Conference on Information and Communications Technology (ICOIACT)*, pp. 773-777. IEEE (2018)
- [8] Aydin, Zeynep Behrin GÜVEN, and Rüya Şamli. "A comparison of software defect prediction metrics using data mining algorithms." *Journal of Innovative Science and Engineering (JISE)* (2020).
- [9] Dietz, Laura, Valentin Dallmeier, Andreas Zeller, and Tobias Scheffer. "Localizing bugs in program executions with graphical models." *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 22 (2009).
- [10] Hao, Dan, Tian Lan, Hongyu Zhang, Chao Guo, and Lu Zhang. "Is this a bug or an obsolete test?." In *European Conference on Object-Oriented Programming*, pp. 602-628. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, (2013).
- [11] Alon, Uri, Meital Zilberstein, Omer Levy, and Eran Yahav. "code2vec: Learning distributed representations of code." *Proceedings of the ACM on Programming Languages* 3, no. POPL (2019).
- [12] Gu, Xiaodong, Hongyu Zhang, Dongmei Zhang, and Sunghun Kim. "Deep API learning." In *Proceedings of the 2016 24th ACM SIGSOFT international symposium on foundations of software engineering*, pp. 631-642 (2016).
- [13] Allamanis, Miltiadis, Hao Peng, and Charles Sutton. "A convolutional attention network for extreme summarization of source code." In *International conference on machine learning*, pp. 2091-2100. PMLR (2016).
- [14] Mou, Lili, Ge Li, Lu Zhang, Tao Wang, and Zhi Jin. "Convolutional neural networks over tree structures for programming language processing." In *Thirtieth AAAI conference on artificial intelligence* (2016).
- [15] Zhang, Jian, Xu Wang, Hongyu Zhang, Hailong Sun, Kaixuan Wang, and Xudong Liu. "A novel neural source code representation based on abstract syntax tree." In *2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, pp. 783-794. IEEE (2019).
- [16] Huang, S. and Fang. N. "Regression Models of Predicting Student Academic Performance in an Engineering Dynamics Course". Utah State University (2010).
- [17] Hasib, Khan Md, Farhana Rahman, Rashik Hasnat, and Md Golam Rabiul Alam. "A Machine Learning and Explainable AI Approach for Predicting Secondary School Student Performance." In *2022 IEEE 12th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)* (2022).
- [18] Xu, Jie, Kyeong Ho Moon, and Mihaela Van Der Schaar. "A machine learning approach for tracking and predicting student performance in degree programs." *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing* (2017).
- [19] Harvey, Julie L., and Sathish AP Kumar. "A practical model for educators to predict student performance in K-12 education using machine learning." In *2019 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence* (2019).
- [20] Rastrollo-Guerrero, Juan L., Juan A. Gómez-Pulido, and Arturo Durán-Domínguez. "Analyzing and predicting students' performance by means of machine learning: A review." *Applied sciences* (2020).
- [21] Koutina, Maria, and Katia Lida Kermanidis. "Predicting postgraduate students' performance using machine learning techniques." In *Artificial intelligence applications and innovations*, pp. 159-168. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg (2011).
- [22] Buenaño-Fernández, Diego, David Gil, and Sergio Luján-Mora. "Application of machine learning in predicting performance for computer engineering students: A case study." *Sustainability* (2019).
- [23] ElGamal, A. F. "An educational data mining model for predicting student performance in programming course." *International Journal of Computer Applications* 70, no. 17 (2013).
- [24] Watson, Christopher, Frederick WB Li, and Jamie L. Godwin. "Predicting performance in an introductory programming course by logging and analyzing student programming behavior." In *IEEE 13th international conference on advanced learning technologies* (2013).
- [25] Carter, Adam S., Christopher D. Hundhausen, and Oluola Adesope. "The normalized programming state model: Predicting student performance in computing courses based on programming behavior." In *Proceedings of the Eleventh Annual International Conference on International Computing Education Research* (2015).

[26] Araya, Ignacio, Victor Beas, Katrina Stamulis, and Héctor Allende-Cid. "Predicting student performance in computing courses based on programming behavior." *Computer Applications in Engineering Education* (2022).

[27] Verifysoft Technology GmbH https://www.verifysoft.com/en_halstead_metrics.html. (2022).

[28] Hellas, Arto, Petri Ihanola, Andrew Petersen, Vangel V. Ajanovski, Mirela Gutica, Timo Hynninen, Antti Knutas, Juho Leinonen, Chris Messom, and Soohyun Nam Liao. "Predicting academic performance: a systematic literature review." In *Proceedings companion of the 23rd annual ACM conference on innovation and technology in computer science education*, (2018).

[29] Ihanola, Petri, Arto Vihavainen, Alireza Ahadi, Matthew Butler, Jürgen Börstler, Stephen H. Edwards, Essi Isohanni et al. "Educational data mining and learning analytics in programming: Literature review and case studies." *Proceedings of the 2015 ITiCSE on Working Group Reports*, (2015).